

INFLUENCE OF SOCIAL MEDIA IN SELECTION OF AIRLINES

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Abstract:

Social media is a popular trend today, especially among college students. Businesses are always looking for new ways to reach customers, especially ones readying to enter the work force. The last 5 years have been a great journey for India with reference to online growth. The online users in India doubled from 120 million users in 2011 to 278 million users in 2014. Mobile phones also showed remarkable advancement with 900 million mobile connections and 220 million smart phone shipments in India in 2014 (Digital DNA 2014). The year 2014 saw a growth curve in a new government, a new leader and a boom in Internet users. Taking India online as a wheel of India's future, India's online population reaching 278 million users and 44% increase in computer literacy in 2014 (IAMA AND IMRB, October 2014).

Key Words: Accumulated Information, Promotion of Communication, Faithful Information & Differentiation in Opinion

Introduction:

Social media was coined from the two operating words – social and media. Social, in this context, simply means the interaction between individuals of common interest, a group, or even a community. And media as the name implies, is the medium, channel, or platform on which allows for creation and exchange of user-generated contents. Social media is less than two decades in existence but have gained widespread acceptance. In 2003, LinkedIn was launched and this was followed by Myspace and Facebook in the year 2004. Due to the characteristics of Facebook, it received a wider acceptance in social circles more than others. Youtube was launched in 2005 followed by Twitter, followed by others such as Blogging, Google+, Instagram, Pinterest, Podcasting, Snapchat, etc. All these have gained more than one billion users world wide in just over ten years of existence. As the name implies, social media networks meant as sites where individuals could socialize, meet old and new friends and interact with each other. Just as the internet was applied into business organizations from the military, so also the commercial value of social media networks became apparent and gained the attention of business managers and became the best friends of marketers in virtually all organizations with presence on the internet.

Need for the Study:

Social network sites (SNSs) have the potential to fundamentally change the character of our social lives, both on an interpersonal and a community level. Changes in interaction patterns and social connections are already evident among young people, who are the heaviest users of these sites. As adoption spreads to a wider audience, we expect such changes to be amplified across all segments of society. At an interpersonal level, the identity information included in public profiles serves to lower the barriers to social interaction and thus enable connections between individuals that might not otherwise take place. On a community level, the organizing features of these sites lower the transaction costs for finding and connecting with other who may share one interest or concern but differ on other dimensions. Both of these processes have the potential to have positive effects on society at large because they encourage disparate individuals to connect, communicate, and take action. The present age group people are spending more time in social media, they use social media to select products to eat, book cinema tickets, recharge their mobiles, and book tickets for bus, train and airline travel. Thus this study is a modest attempt to analyse the influence of social media in selection of airlines.

Review of Literature:

Trainor et al. (2014) determined a positive relationship between SM technology use and customer relationship performance (CRP) intermediated through social CRM capabilities. Secondly, Harrigan et al. (2014) identified a positive correlation between customer relationship orientation (CRO) of a company and its SM use. Some adaptations were required to represent the role of SM in CRM which is presented in Figure 1. Both aspects have been integrated in one unified model. It is shown that the degree of CRO will correlate 14 positively with SM use which in turn will result in higher CRP via SCRM capabilities. Further the research will compare two perspectives, the company's and customer's perspective, that are each based on the conceptual model. Sarvary (2014) argue companies that use SM as a strategic marketing tool considered the derived demand of their business and use SM to increase brand awareness, establish companies as tough leaders, humanize b2b companies, and connect with their stakeholders. Additionally SM can be used by b2b companies in order to optimize search engine results and increase traffic to their homepages. Swani et al. (2014) claims that

b2b marketers have realized the potential of SM to enhance customer relationships as well as branding and are following in the footsteps of b2c marketers. This is clearly seen by the b2b firm's investments into digital marketing surpassing b2c firms although b2c companies were faster to adopt these tools (Järvinen et al. 2012). To illustrate the adaptation of SM within b2b, the Chief Marketing Officer survey showed a 9.6% increase in SM spending in 2012 which clearly represents the growth in online b2b platforms.

Study Area: This research is carried in the Coimbatore district as it comprises of many traders who were involved in export and Import of various products such as textiles, engineering and other related products.

Objectives of the Study: To analyse the influence of social media in selection of airlines.

Statistical Tools Used: Frequency Analysis, Factor Analysis.

Table 1: Demographic Factors and Travel related information

Gender	Frequency	Percent
Male	578	47.0
Female	652	53.0
Total	1230	100.0
Age	Frequency	Percent
18-30 years	557	45.3
31-45 years	316	25.7
46-60 years	188	15.3
above 60 years	169	13.7
Total	1230	100.0
Educational Qualification	Frequency	Percent
School education	213	17.3
Under graduate	111	9.0
Post graduate	315	25.6
Technical education	453	36.8
medical education	138	11.2
Total	1230	100.0
Purpose of travel	Frequency	Percent
Business	452	36.7
Tour	492	40.0
Education	286	23.3
Total	1230	100.0
Travel Decision maker	Frequency	Percent
The passenger	150	12.2
Secretary office administration	510	41.5
Travel agent	394	32.0
Family	176	14.3
Total	1230	100.0
Travel frequency	Frequency	Percent
1-5 times	594	48.3
6-10	359	29.2
above 10 times	277	22.5
Total	1230	100.0
Type of flight chosen	Frequency	Percent
Economy	452	36.7
Business	492	40.0
Premium	286	23.3
Total	1230	100.0

- ✓ Panel 1 explains the Gender group of the respondents, from the panel it was understood that 53.0 percent of the respondents belongs to Panel female and 47.0 percent of the respondents belongs to male.
- ✓ Panel 2 presents the information of the age group of the respondents it can be inferred that 45.3 percent of the respondents belongs to 18-30 years of age, 25.7 percent of the respondents belongs to 31-45 years of age, 15.3 percent of the respondents belongs to 46-60 years of age and 13.7 percent of the respondents belongs to above 60 years of age.
- ✓ Panel 3 presents the details of the educational qualification of the respondents from the table it was understood that 36.8 percent of the respondents educational qualification is technical education, 25.6 percent of the respondents educational qualification is post graduate, 17.3 percent of the respondents

educational qualification is school education, 11.2 percent of the respondents educational qualification is medical education and 9.0 percent of the respondents educational qualification is under graduate.

- ✓ Panel 4 presents the information pertaining to the purpose of travel, and it is inferred from the table that 40.0 percent of the respondent's purpose of travel is for Tour, 36.7 percent of the respondent's purpose of travel is for business and 23.3 percent of the respondent's purpose of travel is for Education.
- ✓ Panel five explains the details pertaining to decision maker regarding the travel, it can be inferred that 41.5 percent of the respondents travel decision maker is secretary office administration, 32.0 percent of the respondents travel decision maker is Travel agent, 14.3 percent of the respondents travel decision maker is family and 12.2 percent of the respondents travel decision maker is the passenger.
- ✓ Panel 6 explains the frequency of travel, From the panel, it can be inferred that 48.3 percent of the respondents travel 1-5 times, 29.2 percent of the respondents travel 6-10 times and 22.5 percent of the respondents travel above 10 times.
- ✓ Panel 7 explains the flight chosen for travelling, from the table it was understood that 40.0 percent of the respondents choose business flight, 36.7 percent of the respondents choose economy flight and 23.3 percent of the respondents choose premium flight.

Table 2: Mobile and Internet related Information

Mobile	Frequency	Percent
Nokia	451	36.7
Samsung	226	18.4
Micromax	338	27.5
Sony	168	13.7
Others	47	3.8
Total	1230	100
Mobile Operator	Frequency	Percent
Airtel	75	6.1
Vodafone	438	35.6
Idea	304	24.7
Aircel	251	20.4
Others	162	13.2
Total	1230	100
Type of Facilities	Frequency	Percent
2G	286	23.3
3G	347	28.2
4G	329	26.7
All	268	21.8
Total	1230	100
Use of Mobile Internet	Frequency	Percent
Mobile data	753	61.2
Wifi	151	12.3
Both	326	26.5
Total	1230	100

- ✓ Panel1 explains the information pertaining to the type of Mobile operated, from the table it was understood that 36.7 percent of the respondents use Nokia mobile, 27.5 percent of the respondents use Micromax, 18.4 percent of the respondents use Samsung mobile, 13.7 percent of the respondents use Sony and 3.8 percent of the respondents use other type of mobiles.
- ✓ Panel 2 explains the information relating to the type of operator selected from the panel, it can be inferred that 35.6 percent of the respondents mobile operator is Vodafone, 24.7 percent of the respondents mobile operator is Idea, 20.4 percent of the respondents mobile operator is Aircel, 13.2 percent of the respondents mobile operator is Others and 6.1 percent of the respondents mobile operator is Airtel.
- ✓ Panel3 explains the type of operator chosen and the type of network used , from the table it was understood that 28.2 percent of the respondent's operators provide 3G, 26.7 percent of the respondents operators provide 4G, 23.3 percent of the respondents operators provide 2G and 21.8 percent of the respondents provide all type of speed.
- ✓ Panel 4 explains the form using the network or internet, from the panel, it can be inferred that 61.2 percent of the respondents use mobile internet through mobile data, 26.5 percent of the respondents use mobile internet through both internet & wifi and 12.3 percent of the respondents use mobile internet through wifi.

Factorisation of Influence of Social Media in Selection of Airlines:

Factor analysis was applied to condense the variables or items into minimum number of manageable items or variables. Factor Analysis has been done with the two statistical tests of Bartlett's test and KMO test. The Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin (KMO) test of sampling adequacy signifies the proportionate variance of variables or items which may be caused through new factors. KMO value in excess of 0.50 reveals that factor analysis is absolutely apt for the particular data set. KMO and Bartlett's Test results are depicted in the below table.

Table 3: KMO and Bartlett's Test

Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin Measure of Sampling Adequacy.		.765
Bartlett's Test of Sphericity	Approx. Chi-Square	8824.407
	df	190
	Sig.	.000

The KMO value of 0.765 implies that the factor analysis applied for this data is valid. The significance value being less than 0.01 implies that the value is significant at 99 % level of confidence. The chi square value for Bartlett's test of Sphericity is 8824.407. High Chi-square value denotes that the variables have been aptly factored. Principal Component Analysis was used for extraction purpose, and varimax rotation is used as the standard rotation. Factors having greater than one as Eigen value are taken as reduced factors which now use as new factors for future analysis.

Table 4: Communalities

Influence of social media in selection of airlines	Initial	Extraction
It is very easy to search about the airlines through internet	1.000	.498
The information provided is less biased	1.000	.541
Social media promotions are more time efficient and good more than mass media	1.000	.651
The social media promotes two way communication	1.000	.736
I always look up for the information provided in social media before getting tickets from airline	1.000	.662
Social media advertisements details the availability	1.000	.582
The information provided by the airline through social media is more objective and credible	1.000	.586
The social media gives more truthful information	1.000	.324
Social media has more effect as your levy on friends opinion	1.000	.613
Lot of information is provided through social media	1.000	.661
Social media gives an opportunity to know a lot of different opinions of real consumers	1.000	.365
Genuine comments are posted in social media	1.000	.256
Social media provide space for posting truth	1.000	.411
The social media makes to know about the personal opinions of airline passengers	1.000	.574
Information provided by social media is accrued	1.000	.692
The quantity and quality of the information provided by the airlines through social media is adequate	1.000	.738
In social media, trust worthiness is more	1.000	.702
More information is provided to customers	1.000	.606
The information provided is more realistic	1.000	.767
The feelings of the end user is dumped in social media	1.000	.698
Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis.		

The variance and eigen value extracted through each factor of Influence of social media in selection of airlines are shown in Table 5.

Table 5: Total Variance Explained

Component	Initial Eigenvalues			Extraction Sums of Squared Loadings			Rotation Sums of Squared Loadings		
	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %
1	5.011	25.054	25.054	5.011	25.054	25.054	3.207	16.034	16.034
2	2.286	11.432	36.486	2.286	11.432	36.486	2.475	12.376	28.410
3	1.714	8.570	45.056	1.714	8.570	45.056	2.177	10.883	39.293
4	1.374	6.868	51.924	1.374	6.868	51.924	2.065	10.323	49.616
5	1.279	6.393	58.317	1.279	6.393	58.317	1.740	8.702	58.317
6	1.146	5.732	64.050						
7	1.004	5.022	69.071						

8	.898	4.490	73.561						
9	.864	4.319	77.880						
10	.679	3.395	81.275						
11	.625	3.124	84.399						
12	.489	2.447	86.846						
13	.442	2.210	89.055						
14	.427	2.137	91.192						
15	.355	1.774	92.966						
16	.316	1.580	94.546						
17	.312	1.559	96.105						
18	.292	1.458	97.563						
19	.258	1.288	98.851						
20	.230	1.149	100.000						

Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis.

Only those components are considered as principal components which have an eigen value greater than 1. Here, the first five components have an eigen value of more than 1, which explains 58.317% of total variance, and the remaining components explain 41.683% of total variance. The below table presents the total variance of the observed variables explained by each of the principal components / factors. For arriving at possible factors from total 20 variables, rotation was converged in 15 iterations through Varimax Rotation Technique.

Table 6: Rotated Component Matrix^a

Influence of social media in selection of airlines	Component					Labeled as
	1	2	3	4	5	
The information provided by the airline through social media is more objective and credible – Inf7	.747					I (16.034) Information through social media
Social media advertisements details the availability – Inf6	.711					
The information provided is less biased – Inf2	.621					
I always look up for the information provided in social media before getting tickets from airline – Inf5	.618					
It is very easy to search about the airlines through internet – Inf1	.585					
The social media gives more truthful information – Inf8	.530					
Social media provide space for posting truth – Inf13	Not Rotated					
The quantity and quality of the information provided by the airlines through social media is adequate – Inf16		.837				II (28.410) Accumulated information
In social media, trust worthiness is more – Inf17		.767				
Information provided by social media is accrued – Inf15		.713				
Social media promotions are more time efficient and good more than mass media – Inf3			.714			III (39.293) Promotion of Communication
The social media promotes two way communication – Inf4			.687			

The social media makes to know about the personal opinions of airline passengers – Inf14		.629		
Genuine comments are posted in social media – Inf12	Not Rotated			
The information provided is more realistic – Inf19		.840		IV (49.616) Faithful information
The feelings of the end user is dumped in social media – Inf20		.810		
More information is provided to customers – Inf18		.543		
Lot of information is provided through social media – Inf10			.785	V (58.317) Differentiation in opinions
Social media has more effect as your levy on friends opinion – Inf9			.673	
Social media gives an opportunity to know a lot of different opinions of real consumers – Inf11			.535	
Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis. Rotation Method: Varimax with Kaiser Normalization.a. Rotation converged in 15 iterations.				

Factor 1 – Information Through Social Media: The variables, The information provided by the airline through social media is more objective and credible – Inf7, Social media advertisements details the availability – Inf6, The information provided is less biased – Inf2, I always look up for the information provided in social media before getting tickets from airline – Inf5, It is very easy to search about the airlines through internet – Inf1 and The social media gives more truthful information – Inf8 constitute factor I which accounts for 16.034 % of variance.

Factor 2 – Accumulated Information: The variables, The quantity and quality of the information provided by the airlines through social media is adequate – Inf16, In social media, trust worthiness is more – Inf17 and Information provided by social media is accrued – Inf15 constitute factor II which accounts for 28.410% of variance.

Factor 3 – Promotion of Communication: The variables, Social media promotions are more time efficient and good more than mass media – Inf3, The social media promotes two ways communication – Inf4 and the social media makes to know about the personal opinions of airline passengers – Inf14 constitute factor III which accounts for 39.293% of variance.

Factor 4 – Faithful Information: The variables, the information provided is more realistic – Inf19, The feelings of the end user is dumped in social media – Inf20 and more information is provided to customers – Inf18 constitute factor IV which accounts for 49.616% of variance.

Factor 5 – Differentiation in Opinion: The variables, Lot of information is provided through social media – Inf10, Social media has more effect as your levy on friends opinion – Inf9 and Social media gives an opportunity to know a lot of different opinions of real consumers – Inf11 constitute factor V which accounts for 58.317% of variance.

Analysis of Variance:

H₀: There is no significant difference between Influence of social media in selection of airlines and Gender.

H₁: There is significant difference between Influence of social media in selection of airlines and Gender.

Table 7: ANOVA

Source of Variance		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Result
Information through social media	Between Groups	2.435	1	2.435	3.251	.072	NS
	Within Groups	919.883	1228	.749			
	Total	922.318	1229				
Accumulated Information	Between Groups	.012	1	.012	.017	.896	NS
	Within Groups	852.146	1228	.694			
	Total	852.158	1229				

Promotion of Communication	Between Groups	11.835	1	11.835	17.399	.000	S
	Within Groups	835.289	1228	.680			
	Total	847.124	1229				
Faithful information	Between Groups	.536	1	.536	.540	.463	NS
	Within Groups	1218.053	1228	.992			
	Total	1218.589	1229				
Differentiation in opinion	Between Groups	27.124	1	27.124	54.079	.000	S
	Within Groups	615.915	1228	.502			
	Total	643.039	1229				

Source: Primary data, * Significant at 5 percent level of significance

The above table indicates that Influence of social media in selection of airlines have significant differences across gender in respect of promotion of communication and Differentiation in opinion factors whereas other influencing factors such as Information through social media, Accumulated Information and Faithful information do not have significant difference with gender. Hence, the null hypothesis is rejected with respect to promotion of communication and Differentiation in opinion factors whereas the alternative hypothesis (H₁) is rejected with respect to Information through social media, Accumulated Information and Faithful information factors.

H₀: There is no significant difference between Influence of social media in selection of airlines and Age.

H₁: There is significant difference between Influence of social media in selection of airlines and Age.

Table 8: ANOVA

Source of Variance		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Result
Information through social media	Between Groups	59.640	3	19.880	28.253	.000	S
	Within Groups	862.678	1226	.704			
	Total	922.318	1229				
Accumulated Information	Between Groups	11.467	3	3.822	5.574	.001	S
	Within Groups	840.691	1226	.686			
	Total	852.158	1229				
Promotion of Communication	Between Groups	22.479	3	7.493	11.140	.000	S
	Within Groups	824.645	1226	.673			
	Total	847.124	1229				
Faithful information	Between Groups	29.284	3	9.761	10.063	.000	S
	Within Groups	1189.305	1226	.970			
	Total	1218.589	1229				
Differentiation in opinion	Between Groups	21.202	3	7.067	13.933	.000	S
	Within Groups	621.837	1226	.507			
	Total	643.039	1229				

Source: Primary data, * Significant at 5 percent level of significance

The above table indicates that Influence of social media in selection of airlines have significant differences across age in respect of all the factors. Hence, the null hypothesis is rejected with respect to all the factors.

H₀: There is no significant difference between Influence of social media in selection of airlines and Educational Qualification.

H₁: There is significant difference between Influence of social media in selection of airlines and Educational Qualification.

Table 9: ANOVA

Source of Variance		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Result
Information through social media	Between Groups	29.045	4	7.261	9.958	.000	S
	Within Groups	893.273	1225	.729			
	Total	922.318	1229				
Accumulated Information	Between Groups	29.612	4	7.403	11.025	.000	S
	Within Groups	822.545	1225	.671			
	Total	852.158	1229				
Promotion of Communication	Between Groups	49.260	4	12.315	18.908	.000	S
	Within Groups	797.864	1225	.651			
	Total	847.124	1229				
Faithful	Between Groups	2.334	4	.584	.588	.672	NS

information	Within Groups	1216.255	1225	.993			
	Total	1218.589	1229				
Differentiation in opinion	Between Groups	13.206	4	3.302	6.421	.000	S
	Within Groups	629.833	1225	.514			
	Total	643.039	1229				

Source: Primary data, * Significant at 5 percent level of significance

The above table indicates that Influence of social media in selection of airlines have significant differences across Educational qualification in respect of Information through social media, Accumulated information, promotion of communication and Differentiation in opinion factors whereas other influencing factors such as Faithful information do not have significant difference with Educational Qualification. Hence, the null hypothesis is rejected with respect to Information through social media, Accumulated information, promotion of communication and Differentiation in opinion factors whereas the alternative hypothesis (H1) is rejected with respect to Faithful information factors.

H₀: There is no significant difference between Influence of social media in selection of airlines and Purpose of travel.

H₁: There is significant difference between Influence of social media in selection of airlines and Purpose of travel.

Table 10: ANOVA

Source of variance		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Result
Information through social media	Between Groups	22.072	2	11.036	15.041	.000	S
	Within Groups	900.247	1227	.734			
	Total	922.318	1229				
Accumulated Information	Between Groups	.148	2	.074	.107	.899	NS
	Within Groups	852.009	1227	.694			
	Total	852.158	1229				
Promotion of Communication	Between Groups	14.854	2	7.427	10.950	.000	S
	Within Groups	832.270	1227	.678			
	Total	847.124	1229				
Faithful information	Between Groups	8.364	2	4.182	4.240	.015	S
	Within Groups	1210.225	1227	.986			
	Total	1218.589	1229				
Differentiation in opinion	Between Groups	7.629	2	3.815	7.366	.001	S
	Within Groups	635.410	1227	.518			
	Total	643.039	1229				

Source: Primary data, * Significant at 5 percent level of significance

The above table indicates that Influence of social media in selection of airlines have significant differences across purpose of travel in respect of Information through social media, promotion of communication, Faithful information and Differentiation in opinion factors whereas other influencing factors such as Accumulated information do not have significant difference with Purpose of travel. Hence, the null hypothesis is rejected with respect to Information through social media, promotion of communication, Faithful information and Differentiation in opinion factors whereas the alternative hypothesis (H1) is rejected with respect to Accumulated information factor.

H₀: There is no significant difference between Influence of social media in selection of airlines and Travel decision maker.

H₁: There is significant difference between Influence of social media in selection of airlines and Travel decision maker.

Table 11: ANOVA

Source of variance		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Result
Information through social media	Between Groups	36.243	3	12.081	16.716	.000	S
	Within Groups	886.075	1226	.723			
	Total	922.318	1229				
Accumulated Information	Between Groups	24.826	3	8.275	12.263	.000	S
	Within Groups	827.332	1226	.675			
	Total	852.158	1229				
Promotion of Communication	Between Groups	13.014	3	4.338	6.376	.000	S
	Within Groups	834.110	1226	.680			
	Total	847.124	1229				

Faithful information	Between Groups	25.248	3	8.416	8.646	.000	S
	Within Groups	1193.341	1226	.973			
	Total	1218.589	1229				
Differentiation in opinion	Between Groups	23.649	3	7.883	15.603	.000	S
	Within Groups	619.390	1226	.505			
	Total	643.039	1229				

Source: Primary data, * Significant at 5 percent level of significance

The above table indicates that Influence of social media in selection of airlines have significant differences across travel decision maker in respect of all the factors. Hence, the null hypothesis is rejected with respect to all the factors.

H₀: There is no significant difference between Influence of social media in selection of airlines and Travel frequency.

H₁: There is significant difference between Influence of social media in selection of airlines and Travel frequency.

Table 12: ANOVA

Source of variance		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Result
Information through social media	Between Groups	17.750	2	8.875	12.038	.000	S
	Within Groups	904.569	1227	.737			
	Total	922.318	1229				
Accumulated Information	Between Groups	24.578	2	12.289	18.220	.000	S
	Within Groups	827.579	1227	.674			
	Total	852.158	1229				
Promotion of Communication	Between Groups	14.253	2	7.127	10.499	.000	S
	Within Groups	832.871	1227	.679			
	Total	847.124	1229				
Faithful information	Between Groups	25.880	2	12.940	13.312	.000	S
	Within Groups	1192.709	1227	.972			
	Total	1218.589	1229				
Differentiation in opinion	Between Groups	27.191	2	13.595	27.087	.000	S
	Within Groups	615.848	1227	.502			
	Total	643.039	1229				

Source: Primary data, * Significant at 5 percent level of significance

The above table indicates that Influence of social media in selection of airlines have significant differences across travel frequency in respect of all the factors. Hence, the null hypothesis is rejected with respect to all the factors.

H₀: There is no significant difference between Influence of social media in selection of airlines and Type of flight chosen.

H₁: There is significant difference between Influence of social media in selection of airlines and Type of flight chosen.

Table 13: ANOVA

Source of variance		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Result
Information through social media	Between Groups	22.072	2	11.036	15.041	.000	S
	Within Groups	900.247	1227	.734			
	Total	922.318	1229				
Accumulated Information	Between Groups	.148	2	.074	.107	.899	NS
	Within Groups	852.009	1227	.694			
	Total	852.158	1229				
Promotion of Communication	Between Groups	14.854	2	7.427	10.950	.000	S
	Within Groups	832.270	1227	.678			
	Total	847.124	1229				
Faithful information	Between Groups	8.364	2	4.182	4.240	.015	S
	Within Groups	1210.225	1227	.986			
	Total	1218.589	1229				
Differentiation in opinion	Between Groups	7.629	2	3.815	7.366	.001	S
	Within Groups	635.410	1227	.518			
	Total	643.039	1229				

Source: Primary data, * Significant at 5 percent level of significance

The above table indicates that Influence of social media in selection of airlines have significant differences across type of flight chosen in respect of Information through social media, promotion of communication, Faithful information and Differentiation in opinion factors whereas other influencing factors such as Accumulated information do not have significant difference with type of flight chosen. Hence, the null hypothesis is rejected with respect to Information through social media, promotion of communication, Faithful information and Differentiation in opinion factors whereas the alternative hypothesis (H1) is rejected with respect to Accumulated information factor.

Conclusion:

The present age of Communication is ruled by social media, and this has led the airlines to advertise their product and promotion mix through social media. This article has studied the influence of social media in selection of airlines. The factor analysis has proved that the influence has made significant impacts on the information through social media, Accumulated information, Promotion of communication, Faithful Information, and Differentiation in opinion. When the factor groups were analysed through ANOVA, and the factor groups were almost significant with the variables of gender, age, educational qualification, purpose of travel, decision making, frequency of travel, and type of flight chosen and the variable educational qualification over faithful information, frequency of travel over accounted information show non significance.

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